

JUSTIFICATION OF THE FINAL CONTOUR OF OPEN-PIT MINING AT THE ANGREN BROWN COAL DEPOSIT

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The key word:Annatation: Currently, the mining industry is the main and major industrial sector in the development of the country's economy. The development of the mining industry serves to meet the needs of other industries and the national economy at a high level. In this regard, the importance of large industrial enterprises of our country, the Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine, the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine, and the Uzbekcoal Joint-Stock Company is incomparable. Taking into account these aspects, this article considers the transition to a combined method of mining promising reserves of the Angrensky section within the framework of the Uzbekcoal Joint-Stock Company. The main factors that should be taken into account when switching the Angrensky Mine from open-pit to underground coal mining are occupational safety from a technical point of view, and the operation of the enterprise at a high level of profitability from an economic point of view. from the point of view of the contribution of the national economy to coal products to meet demand, integrated development of underground resources, etc.

Keyword: Angrensky section, excavators of the type EKG-4u, EKG-5u, EKG-8us, EKG-15, EKG-15M (16,5), BelAz110t, BelAZ 45t, Howo 40t. PE-2U, 2VS-105.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekcoal JSC produces more than 5 million tons of coal annually. The main consumer of coal fuel is the electric power sector, which accounts for over 85 percent of total coal consumption. The demand for solid fuels is also formed by industrial enterprises, social and communal spheres, and the population.

The main factor in the priority development of the coal industry is the expediency of replacing energy resources such as natural gas and petroleum products used in electricity production in the domestic market, and increasing the share of coal in the structure of the energy balance of Uzbekistan.

In the socio-economic development of independent Uzbekistan, which has taken its place on the world map, a special role belongs to the coal industry as one of the main branches of the national economy. In the city of Angren alone,

which is considered a rich base of natural resources, millions of tons of "black gold" are mined. For more than 75 years, Uzbekcoal JSC has been providing the country with "black gold" and has its rightful place among the largest enterprises of the republic.

The main production activity of Uzbekcoal JSC is the extraction of brown and associated minerals. Currently, Uzbekcoal JSC includes the following enterprises with a location in Angren, Tashkent region: The main mining unit in the Uzbekcoal JSC system is the Angrensky mine.

The Angrensky section has been under development since 1948.

The Angrensky section is located 110 km south-east of Tashkent in the foothill valley of the Akhangaran River at the junction of the Chatkal and Kuramin ranges. The coal deposit is located in the floodplain of the Akhangaran River and stretches for almost 40 km along the river valley. The deposit is characterized by a complex tectonic structure, complicated by folded structures of anticlinal, synclinal occurrence, complicated by discharges, tectonic disturbances in the form of ancient and active landslides

Fig. 1. Situational plan with the boundary of the mining allotment of Uzbekcoal JSC

The overburden layer is divided into an external and an internal one.

The rocks of the external overburden (from Quaternary to deposits of the Jurassic coal roof) are represented by boulder-pebble deposits, conglomerates, siltstones, sandstones, marls, limestones, clays.

The bedrock – limestones and marls (Paleogene, Turkestan and Alai), siltstones (Neogene), gravelites and sandstones (Cretaceous) are worked using BVR.

The total volume of rocks subject to blasting for shaking is about 22%.

Clays, siltstones, sandstones, Jurassic sediments are processed without the use of BVR.

The rocks of the internal overburden (Jurassic coal) represented by clays and interangular clays are also worked out without the use of BVR.

Railway showdown

Railway stripping covers volumes from horizon to horizon; excavators such as EKG-4u, EKG-5u, EKG-8us, EKG-15, EKG-15M (16.5) are involved in stripping operations with loading into railway transport.

Railway transport is represented by PE-2U electric locomotives with traction units and 2BC-105 dumpcars. The average capacity of the turntable consisting of 2 motor dumpcars and 8 dumpcars 2VS-105 is 455 m³ in geometric volume.

Car showdown

With loading on motor vehicles, horizons are being worked out from, in view of the remoteness of the dumps, road transport delivers the rock mass to bunkers for transshipment to railway transport with transportation to external dumps;

Also, with loading on vehicles, the rocks of internal stripping are worked out, placed on the horizons from. At these horizons, selective extraction of internal overburden is used during mining operations.

Excavators of the EKG-4u, EKG-5u, EKG-8us, EKG-15M (16.5) types are involved in stripping operations with loading into motor vehicles.

Overburden road transport is represented by the following models:

BelAZ 110t, BelAZ 45t, Howo 40t.

Conveyor stripping

It is used on the southern rounding of the incision. Stripping operations with loading into conveyor transport covered the thickness of the massif from quaternary sediments to limestone soil at pickets from -2 to 10.

Excavators of the EKG-15M (16.5) type are involved in overburden operations with loading into conveyor transport.

Conveyor transport is represented by mobile crushers, inter-stage loaders, downhole conveyor lines with a belt width of 1200mm and a capacity of

4000t/hour, trunk lines with a belt width of 2000mm and a capacity of 12100t/hour.

Due to a significant increase in the volume of stripping operations, it was decided to purchase electric-hydraulic excavators "straight shovel" Hitachi EX 3600-6 with a bucket capacity of 22 m³ or equipment of other manufacturers similar in power and parameters.

In mining operations, the use of Liebherr PR 754 bulldozers, K-700 wheeled bulldozers, or equipment of other manufacturers similar in power and parameters is provided as auxiliary equipment.

In order to intensify the performance of stripping operations, it was decided to involve specialized contractors with the necessary mining and technological equipment, experience in fields with similar mining and geological conditions, to perform a complex of stripping operations (excavation, loading, transportation, maintenance of roads, faces, dumps) with a volume of at least 10 million m³ per year starting in 2021.

At the same time, the volumes and directions of mining operations are issued to the contractor and controlled by the relevant services of Uzbekcoal JSC.

Mining operations

The coal deposit consists of 2 coal complexes: "Powerful complex" - MK, "Upper complex" - VK.

The MK is represented by a homogeneous coal seam with an average capacity of 31.5 meters.

VK is represented by a suite of coal seams interspersed with layers of inter-coal clay. The thickness of the coal layers varies from 0.1 to 3 meters, and therefore, the VC is worked out selectively. The total capacity of the VC, together with the rock layers, is about 35 meters.

The coal seams in the complexes are relatively stable in power, but with different angles of incidence, in some areas of the mining front from 3 to 20 degrees.

The Upper complex is being worked out by 2 10-meter ledges with EKG-4u and EKG-5u excavators with selective mining and loading of coal and host rocks onto technological vehicles (MAN 25t). The average width of the completed approaches is 25m. Coal seams with a capacity of 1.0 m or more are developed by excavators without cutting the host rocks onto vehicles that transport coal to an averaging bunker, coal from formations with a capacity of less than 1 m, clogged with rock during their excavation, also enters there. The mixing process

is carried out in the averaging hopper. Further, coal is reloaded onto conveyor lines through which it is delivered to the PSK "Dzhigiristan".

The "Powerful complex" is worked out with 3 coal ledges up to 15 m high, with an average width of 23 m, excavators EKG-4u, EKG-5u with loading on vehicles (MAN 25t) and transportation to transshipment points on conveyor belts the lines through which coal is delivered to the PSK "Dzhigiristan".

Walking excavators ESH-10/70 are used for flanging the treatment space during the extraction of the "Powerful" formation according to the transportless mining scheme.

Mining road transport, as noted above, is represented by a MAN dump truck with a load capacity of 25 tons.

The dredging and loading equipment for mining operations was selected from the condition of equipping the enterprise with existing equipment and the most complete extraction of coal reserves.

Due to a significant increase in the volume of mining operations, it was decided to purchase Hitachi EX1200-7BH diesel hydraulic excavators with a reverse bucket arrangement and a bucket capacity of 7 m³ or equipment of other manufacturers similar in power and parameters.

1. The development of the deposit is envisaged in an open-pit manner. The development system, in accordance with the mining conditions of the deposit, was adopted by a deepening (Prof. V.V. Rzhevsky) with a variable position of the working area and transportation of overburden rocks by combined transport to external and internal dumps.

The general direction of mining operations is frontal, horizontally inclined ledges, longitudinal approaches when performing stripping and mining operations. A selective method of extraction of minerals with separate extraction of balance reserves of coal from the Upper and Powerful coal complexes has been adopted.

2. The overburden layer is divided into an external and an internal one.

The rocks of the external overburden (from Quaternary to deposits of the Jurassic coal roof) are represented by boulder-pebble deposits, conglomerates, siltstones, sandstones, marls, limestones, clays.

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The rocks of the external overburden are represented by boulder-pebble deposits, conglomerates, siltstones, sandstones, marls, limestones, clays.

The "Central" and "Northern" landslide sites are located in the eastern part of the northern side of the Angren coal mine between PK23 and PK38 at a distance of 0.3-0.5 km south-east of the current A-373 Tashkent-Osh highway.

Conclusions

In the course of completing this master's thesis, I considered the issues of determining the boundaries of coal mining by the open method, determining the volume of stripping during coal mining of 8,000 thousand tons per year. with the determination of volumes for coal mining by the underground method. Performed in the Micromine Origin & Beyond 2023 software package. To carry out the work, block models and digitized geological sections were built with the input of well data, stratigraphic sequence and correlation schemes of the Angren brown coal deposit. The calendar plan for the development of mining and stripping operations has been drawn up in accordance with the accepted procedure for working out the field of the site for the entire service life of the enterprise in the period from 2023 to 2058.

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